

In vitro test setup for continuous evaluation of oxygenators for extracorporeal circulation

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Abstract: Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation (ECMO) is essential for treating severe pulmonary and cardiac failure but is associated with significant risks, including mechanical failures and clot formation. This study presents an in vitro test setup for the continuous evaluation of ECMO oxygenators. Utilizing porcine blood and hollow glass microbeads to induce clotting, the setup measures key parameters such as pressure difference, hemolysis index, and gas transfer rates. Results indicate increased pressure difference and hemolysis, with stable oxygen transfer but declining carbon dioxide transfer over time, highlighting the impact of clot formation. The setup offers a reliable framework for oxygenator performance evaluation.

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I. Introduction

Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation (ECMO) is a critical therapeutic measure used for patients experiencing severe pulmonary and/or cardiac failure (e.g. acute respiratory distress syndrome or cardiogenic shock) [1], often serving as a last resort when conventional treatments have failed [2]. Despite widespread adoption and recognition as a standard procedure, ECMO therapy is associated with considerable risks. Complications occur in up to 40.2 % of cases [3], with mechanical failures, predominantly linked to the oxygenator, or clot formation in the ECMO system being the most common [4]. There are several key functional parameters (e.g. gas exchange, hemolysis, and the occurrence of thrombosis) that are used to assess the performance of oxygenators [5]. Test setups designed to evaluate these parameters typically do not operate continuously or focus on examining a specific parameter [6]. Although these approaches enable targeted analysis, they lack the ability to evaluate the interaction of several factors simultaneously, as it is the case in the human body. To improve the overall safety and efficacy of ECMO therapy, a fully automated, systematic and continuous multiparameter evaluation of the extracorporeal circuit, especially in the clinic, must be pursued. As a first step in this direction, this article presents an in vitro test setup for the continuous evaluation of oxygenators, as they play a pivotal role within the extracorporeal circuit.

II. Material and methods

The in vitro test setup (n=1) comprised two continuously operating sub-circuits, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The upper sub-circuit (evaluation loop) included roller pump 1 (Ismatec MCP Process), the oxygenator (Terumo CAPiox FX 05) under test, and the arterial reservoir. The lower sub-circuit (conditioning loop) consisted of roller pump 2 (Ismatec MCP Process), the deoxygenator (Terumo CAPiox FX 25), and the venous reservoir. To maintain reservoir levels, both reservoirs were interconnected via

roller pump 3 (Heidolph PD2506). A thermostat (Labortechnik Meding T200) connected to the heat exchangers of the (de-)oxygenators ensured normothermic perfusate temperature. All components were connected using silicone tubing. The correct gas supply was realized with a gas mixer (QCAL GMS-3CH) and PVC tubing. Measuring equipment for blood flow (Sonotec SonoFlow Co.55), blood gases (Terumo CDI 500), pressure (Harvard Apparatus APT 300), and exhaust gas concentration (ADInstruments Gas Analyser) was integrated.

Figure 1: Graphical representation of the in-vitro test setup with measuring points for hemoglobin (Hb), blood gases (BG), pressure (P), flow (F) and gas concentration (O₂, CO₂)

Blood samples were collected via Luer connectors to enable hemoglobin (Hb) measurement using a spectrometer

(Spectra Max Plus) and calibration of the CDI 500 with a radiometer (ABL80).

The experimental procedure commenced with the collection of 3 liters of porcine blood (slaughter process), which was then anticoagulated with heparin (4500 IU per liter). Subsequently, the system was primed with 1.5 liters of heparinized Ringer's solution. The perfusate was then added to the system and conditioned according to physiological reference values, in compliance with EN DIN ISO 7199:2016 standards. Following the methodology of Sarathy et al. [7], hollow glass microbeads (HGM) were introduced into the system every hour to induce clot formation (200 mg/h). Blood samples were also collected at hourly intervals. The total measurement time of the experiment was 420 minutes.

To account for the varying measurement intervals of the sensors, the mean value and standard deviation were calculated on a per-minute basis. In addition, pressure difference (Δp), oxygen transfer rate (OTR) and carbon dioxide transfer (CTR) of the tested oxygenator, as well as the hemolysis index (HI) [8] for the entire in vitro test setup, were calculated.

III. Results and discussion

A significant increase of Δp across the tested oxygenator was observed, particularly following the addition of HGM. Concurrently, the HI gradually increased from weak (< 0.1) to strong (> 0.5). Both the Δp and HI trends are illustrated in Fig. 2. These findings indicate a significant impact of HGM on red blood cell integrity and clot formation.

Figure 2: Significant increase of pressure difference and hemolysis index

As seen in Fig. 3, the OTR remained largely constant, despite occasional small fluctuations. In contrast, the CTR rate was stable for up to 120 minutes, after which it decreased sharply and fluctuated around 0 ml/min. Based on the findings regarding the Δp , this abrupt decline in CTR could also be due to clot formation, which obstructs the gas exchange surfaces.

Further investigations have shown that in the exhaust gas concentration remained stable, although a slight increase was recorded when HGM were added. After 360 minutes, the concentration rose sharply. The arterial partial pressure of carbon dioxide steadily increased, especially after adding HGM, while the venous partial pressure remained low and constant. This suggests that the manipulation of the test oxygenator reduced its performance.

Figure 3: Significant decrease in carbon dioxide transfer rate with largely constant oxygen transfer rate

IV. Conclusions

The described test setup and detailed experimental procedures provide a robust framework for the systematic and continuous evaluation of oxygenator performance in extracorporeal circulation. The ability to accurately monitor multiple parameters in real time greatly enhances the detection of adverse events and facilitates timely interventions, thereby improving patient outcomes and increasing the overall reliability of the system. Future improvements will focus on enhancing automation, conducting additional experiments to further validate the findings, and refining the system to address any functional limitations of the oxygenator.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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